

Local Government and the Changing Urban-Rural Interplay¹.

H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018. Grant Agreement no. 823961

Interview Report

Dear interviewer,

Please use this document to report on the expert interviews. Please do not summarize more than one interview per interview report. Wherever you have added questions, please add them also in this Interview Report. For any questions or concerns, please contact your local coordinator or logov@eurac.edu

Thank you very much!

Informed consent

See informed consent sheet

Can identifying information be shared with LoGov researchers?	[yes]
Use of real name for quotes?	[yes]
Archiving of non-anonymized audio-recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized transcript of recording	[yes]
Archiving of anonymized interview report	[yes]

Basic information

Date of the interview	02/07/2021
Name of the interviewer	MONEYBA GONZÁLEZ MEDINA
[Name of the expert, check consent above]	GREGORIO PLANCHUELO
Affiliation of the expert	MUNICIPALITY OF MADRID
Position/Job description	Madrid CEO for Citizen's Participation 2015-2019
Gender	MALE
Years of experience	2015-2019
Area of expertise	CITIZEN PARTICIPATION
Rural and/or urban focus	URBAN

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Part A: Introduction and General Questions

CITIZENS' PARTICIPATION UPON THE EXPERIENCE OF "DECIDE MADRID"

1	<p>What characteristics should the information provided have in order to encourage citizen participation?</p> <p><i>The capacity of citizens to propose issues/interventions is very important, because it gives them the possibility to influence somehow the political agenda. Proposals made by the municipality cannot be too complex or technical.</i></p>
2	<p>How are the alternatives proposed to the public identified and are these alternatives ever elaborated by the citizens?</p> <p><i>Participation is based on proposing, deliberation and vote. Citizens can vote initiatives introduced by the local administration (specific decisions or participatory budgeting) but can also propose new initiatives or interventions (citizen initiatives) on their own that can be voted by residents once they have reached the minimum threshold.</i></p> <p><i>Participation is structured in different steps depending on the level of complexity of each initiative. If the decision is proposed by the local administration and is about something simple such as selecting urban furniture, pictures of available options are enough to elaborate the decision and vote. If the decision is more complex, then the participative process has several steps. For instance, in the case of urban planning interventions, it is organized a first meeting with neighbors and technical staff of the municipality and experts. Afterwards, the results are included in a questionnaire open to all residents (the aim is to explore the perception of citizens about what to do/specific requirements). Then, the results of the consultation (that considers previously voted requirements) are included in the bid for proposals aimed to companies (the proposals must take into consideration these requirements). Finally, proposals are shortlisted by a technical committee and submitted for deliberation (through posts on the website) and final citizen consultation to select the proposal.</i></p> <p><i>In the case of participatory budgeting, citizens propose specific interventions both in their neighborhoods or in the city to be voted by citizens. Considering the level of support achieved, proposals are prioritized by the technical staff according to different parameters, namely 1) the municipality has the formal competence to intervene, 2) the proposal is feasible and 3)</i></p>

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	<i>how much does it cost. Once the proposals are evaluated are deliberated and voted by citizens, considering the budget assigned to a specific district.</i>
3	What evaluation tools are implemented to improve people's participation in local decision making?
	<i>Our idea was to address the problem of similar proposals made by citizens through artificial intelligence (AI). Therefore, we initiated a collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute that uses AI (i.e., Multi-Genre Natural Language Inference -MultiNLI). This test allows evaluating similar chains of text and merge large number of proposals with similar content.</i> <i>We also elaborate reports (the interviewer has provided us with the last one) that evaluate the results.</i>
4	What role do associations and organized interest groups play in these participatory experiences?
	<i>In the case of Madrid, there were two different modes of citizen participation: association-based participation (more traditional and based on meetings) and our platform 'Decide Madrid' (participation is possible from home). Each one was steered by different directorates general within the local administration. In the case of 'Decide Madrid', participation is more single citizen oriented. Participatory budgeting is managed by facilitators.</i>
5	To what extent are participatory decisions mandatory for public authorities?
	<i>Citizen decisions are mandatory for the local council/administration. We were permanently monitoring the level of accomplishment of the project. The responsible areas were accountable for it. We identified that in some cases, area managers paid more attention to their own initiatives compared to those one proposed by citizens. To overcome this problem, there was a clear instruction from the mayor: proposals selected in the frame of citizen participatory processes must be prioritized.</i>

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6	What are the most frequent recommendations made by citizens after their experience in these participatory experiences?
	<i>In the case of the participatory budgeting, the most voted proposals were: Battered Women Shelters/Walk-In Centers/Safe Houses; Bike lanes; Library expansion/equipment; and more trees and gardens. All proposals were very supportive and general interest oriented.</i>

Part B: Questions on Specific Practices

'DECIDE MADRID'

8	Which are the main critical aspects/ challenges of this initiative?
	<i>To interrelate a big number of similar citizen proposals and merge them. Tools such as AI were considered to deal with it and the idea was to sign an Agreement with the Alan Turing Institute of UK to work on this issue.</i>
9	And the main strengths?
	<i>As a result, a high number of public decisions (more than 1000) were taken. They were pertinent, useful, and balanced in terms of cost-benefit analysis.</i>
10	Have you identified any specific bias in citizen participation?
	<i>We have identified that residents of right-wing districts tend to vote less through our tool compared to left-wing districts, that value positively participatory tools.</i>

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